

ESTABLISHMENT OF THE STATE ARCHIVE OF KASHKADARYA REGION

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Abstract. This article, analyzes the organization of the Kashkadarya regional state archive, the goals and tasks of the regional state archive on the basis of historical literature and sources.

Keywords: Archive, record, source, archivist, fund, collection, branch, political, social, political, legal, expertise, fundraising, association, documentary, hardware.

At a certain stage of human development, the development of economic and social relations led to the destruction of the primitive community system and the emergence of statehood. Almost at the same time, due to social necessity, writing also appeared. In the process of performing their social functions, ancient states felt the need to create and preserve various documents (laws, decrees, property and tax reports, etc.). In this way, archives were created, institutions that store documents.

The term "archive" is derived from the Latin word "arkhivum", which in Uzbek means "court", "institution". But this word is used in a different sense today. By archive, we usually mean only an institution where documents are stored. The creation and development of archival work in the territory of Central Asia has ancient foundations and is connected with the history of statehood and the establishment of small and large state associations. With the emergence of writing in Central Asia, the practice of recording important events on the surface of some hard objects - walls, stones, ceramics, metal, birch bark, sharpened wooden sticks or wooden boards it has been.

Thus, important events were documented and the tradition of keeping documents was born. It served to manage economic accounting or legal audit, tax control, and ownership relations. Archives are departments of independent institutions, organizations, and enterprises that store documentary materials, as well as collections of documents resulting from the work of institutions, societies, and certain individuals¹. It should be noted that archives as a collection of sources serve the purposes of scientific research, the needs of enterprises, state administration, individuals, and public organizations. The use of archival documents is the foundation of the historian's research. Archival information is of great importance in the development of history in independent Uzbekistan. It is known that in the Republic of Uzbekistan great importance is attached to the development of the science of history, to the objective and impartial study of the historical past. History is the main element in the restoration of spirituality and spiritual development of our country.

Archival science is related to archival documentation work, methods of scientific and technical processing of archival documents and expertise in determining their historical value, the field of activity of historian-archivist scholars and issues of organizing archival scientific reference apparatus, research activities in archives, popularization of valuable archival documents, etc. analyzes issues. As a result of the adoption of the Law "On Archives" by the Oliy Majlis of Uzbekistan in 1999, as a result of the promulgation of a number of laws and decrees in the field of archival work in the republic, many changes took place. Some successes have been achieved in the development of the State Archive Service. Archival work is an activity related to the

¹ Is'hoqov M., Alimova R. Arxivshunoslik. [Toshkent davlat sharqshunoslik universiteti](#), 2020. 3-4 betlar.

organization of storage, accounting, centralization and use of archival documents of state and non-state enterprises, organizations and institutions².

Currently, the Central State Archives of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, State Archives of Andijan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Tashkent, Fergana, Khorezm Regions and State Archives of Tashkent City are operating. They have 55 branches in places. Regional archives mainly store documents related to the local political situation, economic and cultural development of regions and regions in the period after the October coup. The archive service in Kashkadarya is connected with the establishment of the archive bureau in 1926. In 1928, due to the liquidation of the Kashkadarya district and its incorporation into the Bukhara region, the Kashkadarya district archive bureau ceased its activities. On May 23, 1943, by the decision of the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR, the organizational committee for the Kashkadarya region, the archive department of the Internal Affairs Department of the Kashkadarya region, the regional state archive and the district archives were established. In 1960-1964, in connection with the annexation of Kashkadarya region to Surkhandarya, in addition to the city and district archives, the regional archive department and regional state archives were abolished. In 1964, the Kashkadarya region was re-established, and at the same time, its archive department, regional state archive and its divisions were restored. In the same year, the Karshi and Shahrisabz divisions of the regional state archive, Guzor in 1979, and Mubarak in 1995 were established.

The state archive of Kashkadarya region is an organization that stores scientific and historical documents. It is subordinated to the regional department of archival work. Currently, there are state archives in Karshi, Guzor, Shahrisabz, Mubarak, Koson, Yakkabog districts of our region. There are 2,999 collections of special value preserved in the regional state archive, which are documents from 1924-1945. The institution also has collections in 85,727 storage units dating from 1924-2009. In the archive, separate catalogs were created, where evacuees during the Second World War, awarded war and labor veterans, allotment of land plots, personal origin documents are stored.

One of the rarest documents in the archive is a copy of the ancient foundation document written in 1604 regarding the history of our province. The State Archive of Kashkadarya Region is a scientific research institution and is subordinated to the General Directorate of Archives of Kashkadarya Region.

The work of the State Archive of Kashkadarya Region consists of the collection of documents in the archive, ensuring their proper storage, processing, and issuing copies of references and documents. The State Archive of Kashkadarya Region is a scientific research institution. hokimiyat is subordinate to the Archive department, there are Karshi, Guzor, Shahrisabz and Mubarak departments of the regional state archive³.

- Regional State Archives include:
- Documents created in the territory of the region in 1924 and later.
- Documents of World War II veterans and labor veterans.

Copies of newspapers, political, economic, historical and informative literature, historical photo documents about the life of the region:

- Documents of city organizations and enterprises.

² “Arxivlar to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni 1999yil 15 aprel.

³ Historical reference. 70-Fund, 1-inventory. [Permanent storage files. 1-3.](#)

The main tasks of the regional state archive:

- Compilation of documents in the state archive:
- Ensuring proper storage of documents based on accounting and regime:
- Scientific and technical processing of documents:
- Such as providing copies of references and documents.

In 1996, in connection with the establishment of a centralized accounting office, the accounting position was abolished, and now the positions are as follows:

- Director
- Senior archivist
- 2nd category archivist
- Make-up artist
- Fund custodian
- Janitor
- Guard
- Electrician and plumber

Orders, plans, schedules, financial and accounting reports were included in the permanently stored documents of scientific importance.

The main activity of the state archive of Kashkadarya region is to compile the documents contained in the archive, to ensure their proper storage, to process them, to issue references and copies of documents⁴. Processed documents are stored in the regional state archive. In 2015, the archivists of the Kashkadarya regional state archive carried out fundraising work.

In the course of the fundraising work, after examining the collective volumes in 406 storage units of the fund, they were divided into the Soviet and independence periods. During the allocation, documents in 191 storage units were entered in the C 71 background. In total, in the C-71 fund, there are 667 storage units, collections of which belong to the Soviet era. New fund number 653 was assigned to the documents of the period of independence, and 1992-2008 collection of 214 storage units was added. During the new funding period, 261 total of 47 collections were included for 2008-2014. The history of our country was thoroughly studied based on thousands of archival documents, material and cultural objects, evidence, historical events, conclusions were drawn, and based on international experiences, it was reborn in a truthful way. The documents of state institutions, offices, enterprises, organizations, farms and individuals in the region are carefully stored in the state archive of Kashkadarya region. These documents are valuable as they provide rich information about the newest period of our country's history.

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⁴ Historical reference. 70-Fund, 1-inventory. Permanent storage files. 1-2.

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